

Compass for Just & Effective Decision Making In Wind Energy

JUST
WIND
4 ALL

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Energy Read 5

Co-Produced Compass for Decision-Making in Wind Energy Governance

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drift for transition

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Authors: Teun Strikkers, Dr. Filipe Alves, Mikhail Kharitonov,
Jonas Schröder, Prof. Dr. Julia Wittmayer

Review by: Ana Miljanović Rusan (RGI) & Dr. Mariya Trifonova
(ARC Fund)

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Executive summary

The JustWind4All Wind Energy Compass is a participatory methodology for just and effective decision making. Its primary aim is to aid stakeholders in navigating the synergies between justice —ensuring fair and distribution of benefits and inclusion & transparency of the development process— and effectiveness- achieving practical, efficient outcomes in wind energy development. Over the course of 2 years, 6 dialogue sessions and 7 co-creation events across 4 countries, the compass was developed and validated with regional experts from industry, policy and NGOs over various regional and local levels. It proved successful in aiding decision makers in gaining understanding and actionability with regards to justice and effectiveness in wind energy development.

The compass was created as a tool to address the complex challenges of wind energy development, ranging from lengthy permitting processes and strong public opposition to high investment costs. Typically, efforts to overcome these challenges focus primarily on improving effectiveness- such as cost-cutting measures, enhanced subsidies or environmental mitigation strategies. These are important ways of improving wind energy development. However, it can be argued that without a just approach wind energy development cannot be truly effective nor beneficial to most of society. Navigating the intricacies as well as at first glance opposing objectives between just or effective wind energy development, the compass set out to help identify strategies that can be implemented to make the wind energy transition more just and effective.

The compass is specifically designed to support regional decision makers and work with these complex themes and

make them actionable. It leverages a visioning workshop format based on years of transition research. This method enhances co-creation, collaboration, and shared learning, making it adaptable across international, national, regional, and local contexts.

Its flexibility also allows for application beyond wind energy, making it relevant across diverse countries and policy challenges. Participants consistently reported that the tool helped synthesize diverse expertise, foster shared understanding, and guide strategic action in the wind energy transition.

This energy read presents the methodology and its tools, with examples and experiences from co-creation sessions. It also provides a use-guide for facilitators and additional information to host your own compass session.

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Introduction

Wind energy development is a core component of the energy transition and considering justice in wind energy governance is essential for ensuring its long-term development (Jenkins et al. 2016). Procedural justice—establishing fair and inclusive decision-making—builds trust and reduces conflicts, while distributive justice—fairly allocating benefits and burdens—enhances legitimacy and local support. Without these dimensions, projects may face delays, opposition, or fail and are not developed further. Currently, most wind energy development optimizes for effectiveness, for example costs or energy produced – with increasing focus on their justice implications (Newell et al. 2022), see text box below for more detailed information. The compass, a method designed, tried and tested under JustWind4All, builds upon this development by exploring synergies of both justice and effectiveness in wind energy development.

To ensure the compass is well equipped to work on the just energy transition, it itself is based on transition research (e.g. Hebinck & Loorbach 2024). This research field specializes in creating actionable research outcomes to facilitate transitions, the wind energy transition being one of them. Within this field, action research, co-creation, and richness of diverse perspectives are important methods and concepts that aid transitions, no matter at what stage the transitions are in. The compass draws heavily on this research and is as such designed as a co-creative workshop tool, making it possible to work with challenges in various stages in the wind energy transition.

To fully work with the concepts of justice and effectiveness it is important to recognize the regional uniqueness and similarities as well as the stages of wind energy development. For example, the country of Slovenia which has 3 installed turbines has a different context of wind energy development compared to 11.7 GW of installed capacity in the Netherlands (Balkan Green Energy News, 2023; RVO, 2024; RVO, 2025). Both countries do face similar barriers to ensuring just wind energy transitions, such as public acceptance, however due to the regional contexts, a strategy to overcome these barriers and what exactly the vision should be can differ.

Furthermore, decision making often involves uncertainty and ambiguity (Scoones and Stirling 2020). The compass as a problem-solving method should therefore be able to increase the actionability of stakeholders, harness their diverse perspectives and do this in a way where stakeholders strengthen their own perspectives as well as align with their regional uniqueness.

The compass was therefore tested and co-created in a wide array of different contexts. Both regionally and locally in the

Procedural Justice

Procedural energy justice ensures fairness in decision-making processes related to low carbon energy issues. It emphasizes transparency, inclusivity, and meaningful participation of stakeholders in policy and project decisions. This also involves providing access to information, engaging diverse perspectives, and ensuring accountability to promote equitable processes and outcomes in energy governance.

Distributive Justice

Distributive energy justice concerns the fair distribution of benefits and burdens related to low-carbon energy transitions, including governance structures and ownership models over technology, land and infrastructure. It emphasises equitable access to energy resources and ensures that the advantages and disadvantages associated with low carbon energy production and consumption are fairly shared. This concept encompasses considerations of who benefits from energy development, who bears the costs or risks, and how decisions are made to promote fairness and inclusivity in energy transitions.

Effectiveness

Effectiveness is a broad term, relating to how wind energy development projects use resources, achieve targets and impact their surroundings. This could relate to the materials used in construction, development times, but also environmental impact of the materials used to construct the turbines. This definition is broad, so in the compass we use different indicators that each capture a part of this umbrella definition of effectiveness in wind energy development. A selection of the indicators used in this workshop are the following:

- Time (does wind energy development occur timely?)
- Costs (Is wind energy development not too expensive?)
- Resource usage (Does wind energy use resources in a minimal way?)
- Energy security (Does wind energy development improve energy security?)
- Energy production (Does wind energy development improve energy production?)
- Policy goals (Is wind energy development effective in realizing its goals?)
- Environmental impact. (What impact does wind energy have?)
- ... & more

Netherlands, Spain, Portugal, and Slovenia. Focussing on questions around offshore/onshore division, wind energy development at both the near and far future. It honours the local and regional differences and uniqueness. And is designed in such a way that it can be adaptable to any context or region, whether a wind park in the Netherlands or a strategy for wind energy development in Slovenia.

In this energy read you can read the overall steps that make up the compass, including examples and illustrations from our co-creation events. In the appendix you will find a facilitator use guide, examples of information developed we used in the compass & previous iterations.

What is JustWind4All?

The JustWind4All (JW4A) project, funded under Horizon Europe, explores how energy justice can guide a fair and sustainable energy transition. One of its key approaches is the Wind Forum, a network bringing together stakeholders from the local, regional, national, and the European Union (EU) levels across policy, community, markets, and third sectors to meet, collaborate, and exchange knowledge. The Wind Forum has five regional Wind Labs, which serve as testing grounds for innovative approaches and technologies in real-world contexts.

The compass in action

Overview and examples from the field.

The compass is designed as a 3-5 hours workshop format to be used with up to 35 decision makers in the wind energy transition. The overall aim when holding the workshop is to aid decisionmakers in working with challenges and opportunities related to justice and effectiveness in developing wind energy. The compass has five main goals:

1. To provide background information on justice and effectiveness in wind energy development
2. To form a shared understanding of the concepts of justice and effectiveness
3. To co-create a vision of wind energy development based on the present
4. To identify barriers for achieving this vision
5. Select applicable strategies to overcome these barriers.

Most of the workshop is done in breakout groups such that everyone can share their opinion and vision. This chapter gives an insight into the main steps that make up the compass as well providing examples from co-creation sessions. For a detailed overall overview, see Figure 1. A more detailed explanation suited to facilitators can be found in Appendix 1.

Preparation

The compass is designed around the concepts of flexibility and adaptability making it usable in a wide array of different contexts. This however means that comprehensive preparation is needed for it to be a successful workshop.

Preperation

Compass workshop

To inform

Indicators - apply justice & effectiveness

Breakout - groups

Recap and visioning

Barriers

Vision

barriers

Breakout - groups

Strategies

Strategies

Presentation

Summarize

Figure 1: Flowchart using and running the compass workshop

Choosing the right focus

Choosing the right focus is the first step when setting up the compass. It is important to draw upon expert knowledge to specify and tailor the content such that it is in line with regional contexts. Important questions to consider when thinking about a context, is: “what are current barriers to wind energy development in this region?” or “At what stage is wind energy development in this region? And what geographical scale is the most relevant?”.

For example, in Slovenia, current wind farm operations are limited to 3 turbines, indicating more systemic challenges on a national level as well as partial national discourse. A compass session to improve wind energy development at the local scale therefore is not the right context for the compass and therefore should follow the more national context.

In another example, following the North Sea basin, there is a lot of activity, shipping lanes, wind turbine development, tourism, defence. Space, notably a lack thereof, is therefore an important challenge next to participation and rising investment costs, to name a few. A compass session on the North Sea Basin, can therefore be also more overarching, covering as many relevant indicators as possible.

Selecting the focus also informs the so called central question to the participatory methodology providing an effective boundary for it. This question directs both the participants as well the facilitators. This question can be rather broad and should have a future component (date in the future). Such as: How will wind energy development look like in the North Sea basin by 2040? Or in the case of Slovenia, what will wind energy in Slovenia look like in 2040? Thus, for the flow of the session and the quality of the results it is helpful to also focus on a specific deployment area, offshore or onshore, or policy

area. This allows for the rating of indicators, see section 2, to be more meaningful.

Selecting indicators

The compass operationalizes the key topics distributive justice, procedural justice and effectiveness into context-sensitive key indicators – three for each of the key topics. A selection of indicators is made based on a combination of research and expert opinions following the definitions of justice and effectiveness as stated above. It is often useful to link the indicators and the central question where applicable, this allows for a logical coupling of the central questions and indicators.

The indicators are formulated in terms of questions that are answered by a rating on a scale from 1 to 10. One being less effective or just and 10 being more effective and just. Each indicator also has a descriptive explanation to aid the participants in their understanding of the scaling. For example, in Figure 2, the descriptive text for the first indicator is at 1: “Unfair distribution of space” and goes to 10 meaning “Sufficient space for all”.

In Spain for the distributive justice indicators, we used the questions: 1) How is space distributed among different uses? 2) How are ownership, financial and non-financial benefits distributed? 3) How are burdens distributed? see Figure 2. These questions were selected as they capture the definition of distributive justice well as well as being applicable to the Spanish context. For example, the distribution of space is an important topic in Spanish wind energy development discussion. See Appendix A for more examples of indicators used.

The compass workshop

With preparation completed, the compass workshop can commence. This section illustrates the most important steps of the compass workshop. Each section includes the goal of this section and what the process is to get to this goal.

Presentation introducing compass

The compass starts with a plenary presentation. Its goal is to provide background information on justice and effectiveness in wind energy development and create an equal basis for all participants. It contains an explanation of the concept of procedural justice, distributed justice and effectiveness as well as giving room for participants to share their experienced barriers. Depending on the knowledge of the attendees it is helpful to provide background information on the specific context and timeframe chosen. An explanation of the process of the workshop should be included as well as an explanation of the indicators. Following this we found it helpful to provide concrete and tangible examples, see Appendix 2 for examples that we used in our presentations.

Figure 2: Distributive justice indicators used in Spanish workshops.

Participants

The compass being a participatory method, participant selection is vital. Fine tuning participants should be connected to the central question and its focus. For example if the focus is national, it is important to invite national decision makers. Next to this, diversity of stakeholders included in the method improves the quality of the session and its outcomes. While the degree of decision making power can vary between stakeholders, inviting stakeholders from different organizations, both government, local and national, NGOs, developers and grid operators can improve the outcome of the workshop.

Text box: North Sea workshop - Present and future ratings

Present

During the north sea basin session we had two diverse groups. The different colours in Figure 3 represent two breakout groups. It shows that there is a big overlap of expert opinion on the current state of wind energy development in the North Sea Basin. However, there is also some room for a difference in opinion, for example on the distribution of burdens as well as the speed of the permitting process. This difference can be ascribed to the difference in perspective between the stakeholders in the groups. A double rating here indicates that perspectives diverge. While they were selected and composed to be mostly similar in terms of background it shows that while a shared understanding can be fostered it doesn't mean that a consensus is necessarily formed on each indicator. However, some level of consensus was possible between stakeholders of the North Sea and even contributed to the Energy Read on Maritime Sustainable Planning ([Link to energy read](#))

Future

Differences also emerged during the visioning part of the workshop between the groups, Cirrus and Cumulus. For 2030, the Cirrus group found three things to be the most important. First, they emphasized increasing the number of installed turbines (1). To support this they proposed making investment in wind energy more attractive (2), including improving subsidies and facilitating funding for cooperatives.

Scenario for 2030

Scenario for 2030

Figure 3: Text box figure

While also taking care of the environment 3), making sure that there is space for all activities, some hybrid zones but also nature exclusion zones. 4) To do this effectively collaboration is essential between nation states.

The Cumulus group, in contrast, highlighted four aspects for the future. 1) The biggest emphasis is placed on moving towards more cooperative ownership of offshore wind energy. 2) Burdens from offshore wind energy development shall be distributed more fairly. 3) The impact on nature is intended to move from negative to slightly positive. 4) Finally, actors who right now have little or no influence on decisions around offshore wind energy development shall receive more say, to close the gap to more influential actors. This concerns citizens or

the public, who are not yet as involved as professional stakeholder representatives.

The variation in visions, along with the differences observed in the current indicator ratings, demonstrates the power of this workshop format in eliciting a wide range of opinions and perspectives. These possible futures can in turn be used to inform decision-making indicating that there is no single “just” or “effective” path forward; instead, multiple futures are possible. Exploring these visions can lead to more well informed decision-making and addressing challenges in wind energy development more holistically.

Rating indicators for the current situation

The goal of this step is to obtain a shared assessment of indicators from stakeholders, reflecting on the current situation. The process typically involves collective rating during breakout sessions, followed by plenary sharing and discussion. These indicators are a vital part of the workshop, as they guide the conversation and help translate abstract concepts of procedural or distributive justice and effectiveness into concrete, actionable terms. By organizing justice and effectiveness into different indicators, rating them allows for having a focused conversation on these topics, achieving one of the key objectives. An example of this process in the North Sea Basin is illustrated in Figure 3. The scales are constructed subjectively based on expert knowledge and are made to ease conversation and improve understanding of the concepts.

Rating indicators for the future vision

After the participants return from a break, the main facilitator will guide the session by recapping the ratings from each group. This includes highlighting areas of agreement, noting possible overlaps, and exploring reasons for any divergences in the ratings. In the text box, the results from the North Sea basin group are presented as an example of this process.

The goal of this step is to create a vision for each indicator. This section starts with a presentation that first summarizes the current situation and then introduces information or methods that encourage participants to think about future possibilities. For instance, in one of our workshops, holistic impact assessment and energy system modelling were used

to stimulate forward-looking discussions, linking to other JustWind4All activities.

Next, the stakeholders will discuss their own vision by deciding on how many steps they want to move forward. The central question serves as a guiding framework. For example, in the Slovenian demonstration exercise this was: "What will wind energy development look like in 2040?" The chosen year represents the future reference point for participants to evaluate their vision. An additional criterion is added at this stage to help participants prioritize indicators, focus on the most critical actions, and ensure that the envisioned changes are both strategic and actionable.

Barriers

The goal of this step is to collectively identify the barriers that could prevent the realization of the created vision. Participants are first asked to share the barriers they currently experience or foresee in achieving the vision. After discussion, the group uses dot voting to select the most critical barriers. This selection allows the participants to focus on the core barriers that inhibit their vision.

Figure 4 shows the plethora of barriers experienced by stakeholders. Grouping these can show emerging themes can then be addressed by the facilitator in the strategy session.

A selection of perceived barriers from the North Sea basin

Stakeholder engagement in Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) and offshore wind planning must be diverse but can sometimes stall progress due to lack of consensus.

The **relationship between offshore wind, fisheries, and nature protection** is complex; restricting fishing in Offshore Wind farms can enhance nature but might displace fishing and therefore environmental impacts elsewhere.

Fair space distribution in MSP is difficult; stakeholder engagement often excludes nature and citizen voices, and historic users dominate claims. The space distribution will be further complicated by the new **Nature Restoration Law**.

Financial barriers limit cooperative participation in offshore wind projects; strong **government support** (e.g., Belgium's SeaCoop) is crucial.

Ownership and financial benefits are unfairly distributed; cooperatives carry risks without real decision-making power or proportional benefits.

Permitting acceleration focuses on formal steps, but significant delays occur during informal pre-permitting activities (e.g., surveys, stakeholder talks), which are often overlooked.

Nature-inclusive design (NID) and **multi-use technologies** face legal and practical barriers; scaling up requires legal clarity and viable business models.

Strategies

The goal of this step is to give participants strategies to overcome the barriers identified in the previous step. This is done by giving them a compass lotus developed as part of this workshop which contains a wide variety of strategies. Additionally, participants are encouraged to share useful strategies among themselves.

Strategy Lotus

The strategies included on the lotus are formulated on a relatively high abstraction level improving applicability in many different contexts.

The lotus like its namesake opens up to show its content. It is handed to the participants folded to reduce information overload, see illustrations on the right. The lotus starts with several strategic themes and then can fold it out to reveal general strategies. The compass can eventually be folded out completely to show more specific strategies but also examples from the case studies.

A more detailed selection of the strategies can be found here: <https://justwind4all.eu/wind-energy-compass/>

Figure 6: The strategy lotus in stages

Plenary sharing & feedback

The last step of the workshop is to share the vision, core barriers and strategies plenary of each breakout group and to shed light on similarities and differences. This is done by the main facilitator in a plenary setting.

*Summarizing the perspectives on procedural justice in Spain
There is a recognized need for more balanced stakeholder involvement and meaningful public participation in wind energy projects. Presently, stakeholder diversity is lacking in terms of effective participation, raising concerns about power imbalances. A notable issue is that people often understand how to oppose wind projects but are unclear about how to support or co-develop them. This reflects a lack of clarity and accessibility in public participation processes. This interesting as both groups raised that the decision making process is quite transparent highlighting a potential for improved literacy amongst stakeholder groups with regard to the development process.*

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